

iQonic

iQonic

Innovative strategies, sensing and process chains for
increased **Q**uality, re-configurability, and recyclability of
Manufacturing **O**ptoelectronics

Deliverable

D4.1 Automatic Data Collection

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY / ABSTRACT

This D4.1 “Automatic Data Collection” report illustrates the prototype implementation of the automatic data collection infrastructure, which supports data streaming from the lower level (Field devices at ShopFloor) to the high-level functions (PdM, CPS, EvMod, RSC, DSS, KBS) of iQonic system. It also accompanies a set of software packages that realize this implementation. Deliverable D4.1 is therefore devoted to the detailed specification and prototype implementation of the automatic data collection infrastructure, which follows principles of the iQonic *System Architecture* (D2.3) and adheres to the specifications of the WP2 Requirements and conceptual process chain design deliverables.

The overall iQonic concept, as depicted in Figure 1, presents the involved processes and their interconnection. It is functioning in three levels based on relative inspection systems, namely WorkStation Level (WSL), Part Level (PL) and Shopfloor and Plant level (SPL). The WSL will facilitate the collection and interpretation of data produced throughout the production line. This springboard established the overall iQonic data system architecture and data flow (Figure 2), a joint effort of WP4 and WP6.

Specifically, starting from the iQonic data system architecture and data flow, a more detailed specification of the automatic data collection sensorial network is provided in terms of the following functionalities: streaming data in local (ITK Daedalus) and cloud (iLike) level. These functionalities are provided by Data Streaming subsystem. This component is designed in a way that is capable to provide data streams in both ITK Daedalus and iLike platform level

The Data Streaming subsystem links to the data streaming mechanism of iLike machines by Holonix. Data streaming consists of two components: “Routing Transformation Service” (RTS) and “Translators”. RTS provides a communication interface with external platforms, as in this case is iLike by Holonix, in order to receive external requests for data streaming or commands. Furthermore, it is responsible for creating data flows from the data sources to iLike platform, in order to support data analytics in higher level functions of iQonic system. On the other hand, the “Translators” subsystem translates the raw data from the shop floor data sources to the data scheme employed by the iLike platform.

Note that the present version of the deliverable represents the first release of the automatic data collection infrastructure, while a second and final release will be expected during WP7 Integration & Testing -Validation. The final release will provide a complete implementation of the Data Streaming subsystem, including relevant tools. It will also incorporate feedback, received during the integration of the prototypes with other components, as well as feedback from the use of the middleware infrastructure in the iQonic use cases implementation aligned with the “Iterative Feedback approach with users in the LOOP” (IFLOOP), as it was described in the proposal.

Scope

This demonstration report will focus on the sensorial network architecture and the implementation of the data acquisition mechanism throughout the demo cases (D2.4). This report introduces the iQonic field devices, the overall mechanism of data acquisition and the data flow between data sources (endpoints) and the i-Like platform, a core component of the overall iQonic architecture developed by Holonix.

ABBREVIATIONS

Key Performance Factors	KPF
WorkStation Level	WSL
Part Level	PL
Shopfloor and Plant Level	SPL
Technical Objective	TO
Electrostatic Discharge	ESD
Internet of Things	IoT
Cyber-Physical System	CPS
Reverse Supply Chain	RSC
Decision Support System	DSS
Manufacturing Execution Systems	MES
Maintenance Management System	MMS
Enterprise Resource Planning	ERP
Optoelectronics Research Centre	ORC
Laser Diode	LD
Light-Emitting Diode	LED
Augmented Reality	AR
Virtual Reality	VR
Requirement	RQ
Original Equipment Manufacturer	OEM
Human-Machine Interface	HMI
Machine Level Communication Middleware	MLCM
Integra Traceability Kiosk	ITK
Knowledge Base System	KBS
Higher Level Communication Middleware	HLCM
Machine to Machine	M2M
Volatile Organic Contaminants	VOC
Routing Transformation Service	RTS
Representational State Transfer	REST
remote procedure call	RPC
Enterprise Information System	EIS
Ultrasound Machining	USM

1 Introduction

The automatic data collection system, as seen in iQonic concept and approach (Figure 1), acquires data from several data sources spread in multiple steps and processes throughout the opto-electronics assembly and production line. This span, as data sources could be in different, even physical locations and the diversity of the data sources as the assembly line incorporates multiple and different specialized equipment comprise a key challenge. The main objective of the Automatic Data Collection task addresses the development of a continuous monitoring of the condition and performance of the multi-stage opto-electrical manufacturing systems on component and machine level to enable sustainable and competitive manufacturing (O2 [1]).

The data sources live within an asset which is any physical thing that exists in the ShopFloor, being part of the production line and within iQonic needs to be monitored and/or commanded. The system will be deployed at the Work Station Level (WSL) that will facilitate the collection and interpretation of data produced throughout the production line. In this level, the **Reactive Functions** that are intended for fast reaction and close to machine operation will be utilized.

Figure 1: iQonic concept and approach

The iQonic data system architecture and data flow (Figure 2) consists of several hardware (i.e. machinery) and software (i.e. machine learning algorithm) components. In this report, the focus lies on the data flow from the end-user to the i-Like Machines platform developed by Holonix. The i-Like platform is a core component receiving all the data from the shop floor providing a secure authorization mechanism for the higher level functions (PdM, CPS, EvMod, RSC and DSS) to access the data for the execution of the general iQonic strategies [1]. Besides that, it encapsulates the iQonic KBS (D4.5) component and provides historical data as well.

The ITK Daedalus system creates data flows streams among the data sources on the field (field devices) through the Data Streaming [2] subsystem, utilizing relevant connectors and by employing several communication protocols. The acquired data are locally processed, aggregated and through a communication channel based on publish subscribe model pushed to the iLike platform.

Figure 2: iQonic data system architecture and data flow

In addition, processed and/or simulated sensorial data from the Machine Level Communication Middleware (i-Like Machines) and data from Manufacturing Execution System (MES) / Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Systems will be collected through the Higher-Level Communication Middleware (HLCM, D6.4) developed by Atlantis.

A key challenge of the automatic data collection system to overcome is the diversity and disparity of the needed data for the higher-level functions to operate and eventually through its execution to improve quality and yield of opto-electronics industry by fulfilling the general iQonic strategies.

1.1 iQonic WP4 Overview

iQonic's [3] WP4 is devoted to the management of the generated data through the production chain of the opto-electrical manufacturing parts. The management of generated data extends its scope from the actual data source (i.e. sensor) to the meta data layer. In addition, an electronic “nose” (D4.2 *Electronic nose prototype*) will be designed and manufactured by SACMI [4] for the detection of volatile organic contaminants (VOC). An in-line optical control based on adaptive optics (D4.3 *In-line optical control systems based on adaptive optics*) by Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH [5]) for quality inspection of the materials processing and a robotic dexterous hand by Shadow Robots [3] will be employed and further developed (D4.4 *Robotic System for Flexible handling*) for flexible handling within the needs of the iQonic project. Lastly, the iLike machine platform by Holonix [6] will be employed for the connection between the production line (field devices) and the higher functions of the iQonic platform and developed further (D4.5 *iQonic KBS*) performing analysis for supporting defect predictive and prevention mechanism.

This task will mainly focus on the establishment of a distributed sensor network, an essential precondition for using the potentials of inline measurements with maximized efficiency. It will provide the basis for implementing the KPIs calculation and visualization tasks in subsequent work packages by means of collecting all the necessary data emerged through D2.4 Use Case Design. It addresses the relevant requirements depicted

by WP2 (D2.1 User requirements) and is aligned with the overall iQonic architecture based on WP2 (D2.3 iQonic system architecture process chain & Strategies).

The WP4 activities span over the phase 1 of the overall approach and methodology (Figure 3) of the iQonic project. In this phase, all the R&D activities for the development of the project subsystems are included. It is finalized with the developed technologies been tested in the laboratory and are ready for integration (MS5 and MS6).

Figure 3 Overall approach and methodology of iQonic

1.2 Relationship with other Work Packages and Deliverables

The present document is closely affiliated with the following work packages and deliverables (Figure 4):

WP2- Requirements and Conceptual Process Chain Design

- D2.1- User Requirements
- D2.3- Design and architecture of the process chain and strategies
- D2.4 – Use case design

WP3- Opto-Electrical System Design for Assembly and Disassembly

- D3.4 – Inspection & metrology infrastructure to monitor KPIs

WP4- Data management, sensor, and processes design and setup

- D4.2 Odour in-process sensing for organic contamination and material evaluation
- D4.3- Adaptive in-process optics for real-time feedback and thin-layer quality inspection
- D4.4 Development of robotic system for flexible handling
- D4.5 Middleware encapsulating sensors managers & semantic components (KBS)

For the data acquisition system to address the user requirements and successfully collect the necessary data for the rest of the work packages work, we had followed the on-site visits as they organised to the use cases and to ficonTEC. The on-site visits to the use cases provided us with a better in-depth understanding of the opto-electrical processes while through the discussions with the experts among our partners, we defined the necessary data sources and in the use case of Filar, the specific need for additional sensors to be deployed. The visit to ficonTEC demonstrated to us the capabilities of the machine regarding the opto-electronic assembly process and defined a first technical approach in terms of connectivity, as the ficonTEC machine will be utilised and is the main data source for two of our use cases, namely Prima and BrighterWave. A series of teleconferences follows the on-site visits for further clarification and collaboration on the necessary data for the iQonic high level functions. By defining the set of the needed data in each use case and acknowledging the digitalization readiness of each use case, the automatic data acquisition system developed in three-fold.

- Addressing the user requirements
- Defining additional sensors
- Supporting standards and communication protocols already in use by use cases.

Besides the technical challenges of this task in terms of the diversity of use cases digitalization readiness, another hindrance was the data definition (type, format, rate) source needed for the demo cases of each use case.

Figure 4 WP Relationship diagram (Pert type)

1.3 Document Structure

The document structure is as follows:

- Chapter 1 provides an **Introduction** of the deliverable scope and structure and defines the role of this task to WP4 and the related work packages.
- Chapter 2 provides the **Background Information** concerning the design and implementation of the automatic data collection system.
- Chapter 3 is an **Overview of iQonic Multi-Sensorial Network Architecture and Infrastructure**. It provides an architecture of the infrastructure that is responsible for the data collection and streaming to iLike Machines. It includes the supported requirements specification (D2.1) and the Field devices employed in the iQonic system by our Technology Providers. Finally, it analyses the Data Streaming sub-system which is responsible for the management of the data streaming and the registration of the data sources.
- Chapter 4 focuses on the additional **Sensors** that were defined for the use cases.
- Chapter 5 presents **Use Cases** for the automatic data collection infrastructure, i.e. proof-of-concept use cases that can be supported by the middleware infrastructure.
- Chapter 6 presents the **Conclusions** and the next actions related to this task.

2 Background Information

2.1 Multi-Sensorial Network Logical Architecture

The multi-sensorial data acquisition network (Figure 5) at the WSL level of the iQonic system resides in the shop floor (layer 1-3, according to RAMI 4.0 [7]). It includes different types of sensors (i.e., Temperature/Humidity, accelerometers) and machinery (i.e., Electronic nose, ficonTEC AL-500) producing heterogeneous set of data. Daedalus edge controller [8] interfaces with and acquires the raw data, aggregates and translates them into the employed data scheme. The last process step is the transmission of the data package using a predefined format type, through a message bus mechanism (MQTT) to the i-Like machine. The shop floor low level interface of the Daedalus device communicates with the data sources through well-established protocols, such as Modbus, TCP/IP -REST Web Services but also through latest communication protocols, such as OPC-UA and MQTT. The flexibility of the edge device through its modular design (scalability) and the use of open source technologies is aligned with the requirement of the architecture as it was described in D2. *System Architecture*. In addition, the Key Performance Index (KPI) calculations and its Human Machine Interface (HMI) for visualization and alerts, unifies the heterogeneity of the shop floor transforming it into a “smart” shop floor, as industry 4.0 dictates.

Figure 5: Multi-sensorial data acquisition network [9]

The integration methodology for the iQonic platform will be based on the Incremental Integration Strategy (IIS), prioritizing the integration of main components and interfaces. Following this, iQonic will integrate all the hardware components through incremental builds and perform integration tests and validations until the integrated iQonic technological solution is produced. To organize this, a Regression Testing Plan (methodology, definition of the Test Bucket, Test Cases to assess the performance of each component and apply regression testing on any integration iterations) will be defined (WP7-T7.1).

2.2 Supporting Technologies, frameworks, standards and implementations

2.2.1 REST-Web Services

Representational State Transfer (REST) is an architectural style and model that relies on the web standards using Hyper Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) verbs and Unique Resource Identifiers (URIs). The following principles are the foundation of any REST implementation:

- All the resources are identified by URIs;
- All the resources can have multiple representations;
- All the resources can be accessed/modified/created/deleted by standard HTTP methods;

- The connections between client and server are stateless.

The design and implementation of the components based on the REST architectural style follows the following necessary step:

1. Identification of the resource URIs (see Table 1)
2. Identification of the HTTP methods for Create, Read, Update and Delete (CRUD) operations supported by the resource (see Table 2 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**); and
3. Identify the different representations supported by the resource.

Table 1: Sample URI and related description

URI	URI Description
/xxx/yyy/zzz	<i>Describe the resource represented by the URI</i>

Table 2: HTTP methods and action description on the resource

HTTP Method	URI	Action Description
GET	/xxx/yyy/zzz	<i>Describe the action taken on the resource represented by the URI</i>
POST		
DELETE		
PUT		

2.2.2 Integration Middleware

Node-Red

Node-RED

Node-RED [10] is a programming tool that is used “wiring” together hardware devices, APIs and online services in a graphical and thus, very intuitive way. It provides a browser-based editor that delivers all the necessary mechanisms for “wiring” together components and services (also called nodes) while creating execution flows. These flows can be – then – deployed and executed on the top of node.js.

The usage of node.js as execution runtime delivers to node-red event-driven, non-blocking capabilities (inherited from the node.js model) while assuring its execution on low-cost single-board platforms. Furthermore, node-red relies on a very active and vibrant community where nodes and flows are constantly uploaded and shared by node-red developers, allowing to extend more and more the node-red capabilities and functionalities.

MQTT

MQTT [11] is a connectivity transport for lightweight machine-to-machine (M2M) messaging. MQTT uses a centralized broker and supports publish-subscribe communications pattern running on top of TCP/IP, used for telemetry and connecting remote sensors to the cloud and IoT scenarios where small code footprint is required and/or network bandwidth is at a premium.

Modbus Communication Protocol

A well established de facto serial communication protocol created in 1979, initially for connecting PLC controllers by Schneider Electric. Nowadays, it is a means of connecting industrial electronic devices (M2M), and due to its publicly open and royalty free characteristics it is considered very popular. It uses the RS485 standard as its physical layer.

ROS Bridge

A middleware abstraction layer that provides a standard minimalistic application framework for third party application to “talk” to robots using the Robot Operating System (ROS). Essentially it is a set of software libraries and tools for building robots. It provides a simple socket-based programmatic access to robot interfaces algorithms provided by ROS.

2.2.3 Data Representation and Exchange

IEC 62714 AutomationML¹

AutomationML (Automation Markup Language) is another XML-based, neutral and open data format that enables storage and exchange of plant engineering information. AutomationML alleviates the heterogeneity of the various state-of-the-art engineering tools that are used in different areas of industrial automation.

AutomationML is based on a series of other standards and formats including: (i) the previously described CAEX for plant topology representation in an hierarchical manner; (ii) the COLLADA format for representing geometrical information, graphical attributes and kinematics in the 3D space; and (iii) industrial automation logic implemented based on the PLCopen XML format, which provides the means for modelling the dynamic behaviour (e.g., sequences of actions) of the automation system.

AutomationML subsumes some of the above listed formats for plant information representation (e.g., CAEX) and as such it is listed among the RAMI4.0 and Industry 4.0 standards. In iQonic, it can provide a methodology (including reference and use of other schemata) for representing plant information and industrial automation logic.

IEC 62424 CAEX

Similar to XMpLant, CAEX (Computer Aided Engineering Exchange) is a neutral data format, which provides the means for describing a plant and its elements, but also for exchanging data across different process engineering and process control tools. CAEX assumes a hierarchical plant architecture and enables storage of hierarchical object information. It enables an object-oriented approach for plan modelling, as it uses objects to represent the various modules of a plant. Note that CAEX is also an XML format and hence it is defined as XML schema. Elements of the latter schema could be used to structure plant descriptions in iQonic.

IEC 61360

As stated in [12], properties classify a system and can be expressed by means of simple values. In the Industry 4.0 context, information needs to be easily shared between all the actors located in the three-dimensional model of the RAMI 4.0. Although it is not feasible to define a single and universal information model, the application of property models can help in achieving interoperability between systems and software components [13]. Properties can be used to define and communicate the actual state, the actual configuration and/or setting variables, as well as, the capabilities of the system or physical asset. To do that, properties need to be defined in a very generic and unambiguous way. The standard IEC-61360 defines the structure and the necessary elements to be used in order to organize the property itself.

2.2.4 Human-Machine Interface

Telegram

Telegram is a cloud-based instant messaging and voice over IP (VoIP) service developed by Telegram Messenger LLP. Telegram client apps are available for the most common platforms such as Android, iOS, macOS, Windows, Linux, etc. By using these apps, users can exchange messages and files of any type.

¹ <https://www.automationml.org/o.red.c/home.html>

The usage of telegram is extremely interesting especially for the design and implementation of the so-called “bots”. Bots are telegram accounts that are operated by programs allowing software programs to communicate and exchange messages with other programs (bots) and/or human user.

2.2.5 Messaging Integration Patterns

Nowadays, monolithic applications that can meet consumers demand rarely exist. The key concept is for the system design and implementation to be more in a service-oriented approach, in which every service is exposed as a micro-service that “produces” a specific task. The full functionality of the designed system can be achieved by integrating these services. Of course, integration is not just a simple procedure, since we must face different implementations coming from various vendors, for each simple component. Integration patterns come to solve this issue by providing a guidance. In fact, integration patterns are not invented: they are best practices originating from previous integration projects. For the scope of data streaming, we investigate the usage of the messaging integration patterns that are a subset of the integration patterns (Figure 6)

Figure 6 Messaging integration patterns. source: [14]

Why using messaging

The adoption of messaging approach to an integration solution has many advantages:

- Remote Communication: Messaging enables separate applications to communicate and transfer data.
- Platform/Language Integration: Systems are connecting via remote communication, usually use different languages, technologies and protocols. A messaging system can be a translator between these systems, allowing them all to communicate through a common way.
- Asynchronous Communication: Messaging enables "a send and forget" approach to communication. The sender does not have to wait for the receiver to receive and process the message. If the receiver wants to send an acknowledgement back to the sender, this message will be detected by a call-back mechanism on the sender.
- Mediation: A messaging system acts as a mediator between all the systems that can send and receive messages. A system can use it as a directory of other applications or services available to integrate with.
- Reliable Communication: Messaging provides reliable delivery, that a remote procedure call (RPC) cannot, by using a "store and forward approach" for transmitting messages. The data is packaged as

messages that are atomic, independent units. When the sender sends a message, the messaging system stores the message and then delivers it by forwarding it to the receiver.

Basic messaging concept

- **Channels** — Messaging applications transmit data through a Message Channel, a virtual pipe that connects a sender to a receiver.
- **Messages** — A Message is an atomic packet of data that can be transmitted on a channel. Thus, to transmit data, an application must break the data into one or more packets, wrap each packet as a message and then send the message on a channel. Likewise, a receiver application receives a message and must extract the data from the message to process it. The message system will try repeatedly to deliver the message (e.g., transmit it from the sender to the receiver) until it succeeds.
- **Multi-step delivery** — In the simplest case, the message system delivers a message directly from the sender's computer to the receiver's computer. However, actions often need to be performed on the message after it is sent by its original sender but before it is received by its final receiver. For example, the message may have to be validated or transformed because the receiver expects a different message format than the sender. A Pipes and Filters architecture describes how multiple processing steps can be chained together using channels.
- **Routing** — In a large enterprise with numerous applications and channels to connect them, a message may have to go through several channels to reach its destination. The route that a message must follow may be so complex that the original sender does not know what channel will get the message to the final receiver. Instead, the original sender sends the message to a Message Router, an application component and filter in the pipes-and-filters architecture, which will determine how to navigate the channel topology and direct the message to the final receiver, or at least to the next router.
- **Transformation** — Various applications may not agree on the format for the same conceptual data; the sender formats the message one way, yet the receiver expects it to be formatted in a different way. To reconcile this, the message must go through an intermediate filter, a Message Translator, that converts the message from one format to another.
- **Endpoints** — An application does not have some built-in capability to interface with a messaging system. Contrariwise, it must contain a layer of code that knows both how the application works and how the messaging system works, bridging the two so that they work together. This bridge code is a set of coordinated Message Endpoints that enable the application to send and receive messages.

3 Overview Of iQonic Multi-Sensorial Network Architecture

3.1 Multi-Sensorial Network Architecture Objectives

The iQonic sensorial network introduces a novel self-adjustment mechanism through a suitable network management module (O-2), the *Transformation Service* (section 3.3.1). Through this service, the production defect relevant data at the interface of components manufacturing and system assembly hardware, along with the current production state will be acquired and transmitted to the analytic functions of the iQonic platform.

The key functionalities of the Multi-Sensorial network, as were described in the DoA [1], were addressed and implemented in this deliverable as the first version of the system prototype (proof of concept). The system will be finalized during WP7 in *T7.1 Integration of software – hardware platforms and tools*, where the feedback of the user with the additional requirements and the fine tuning of the system will be developed.

Multi Sensorial System Objectives

- Implementation of a data acquisition network for automated collection of data from various operation and maintenance related data sources and systems, including equipment sensors, production systems, production quality systems, shop floor devices and more.
 - Collected data will be based on the data models (and related schemas) specified in WP2 and WP3
 - Installation of the necessary sensors depicted from prior WP's to our edge controller.
- Acquisition network will be based on technologies used in industrial engineering (such as OPC-UA and MQTT), that will enable access to the various systems and subsequently storage of data in appropriate datastores
 - Interfacing with Holonix platform

The system is based on the ITK Daedalus component (Figure 7) managing all the low-level sensorial inputs from various sensors. It aggregates and streams the data through the communication channel to the i-Like platform via its *Transformation Service*. The system achieves near “real” time data acquisition utilizing an industrial programmable logic controller (PLC) that is dedicated to the signal conditioning of the sensors and an edge device hosting the *Transformation Service* and all the high-level functionality of the system. The system offers flexibility in terms of connectivity and scalability as it provides the mechanism for registering new data sources ad-hoc.

3.1.1 Matching User Requirements and Technical Objects

The iQonic *automatic data acquisition* system addresses the following user requirements defined in *D2.1. User Requirements* at iteration -II (M12-M14). The user requirements related to the automatic data acquisition system were investigated and are currently supported in this release. These requirements will be updated at the final Iteration III (M18-M20). The new requirements, if they occur, and the updated ones will be addressed at the integration phase at WP7.

Table 3: Supported Requirement depicted by D2.1 User Requirements at iteration -II (M12-M14)

RQ ID	Title
PR-B-03	Process Monitoring: Disassembly, Remanufacturing & Reuse of the components, currently, these aspects are not managed due to the higher vertical production and the high operating costs.
AT-T-11	Data shall be collected and analysed for monitoring of iQonic strategies implementation.
AT-NT-13	Data shall be collected and organized from pilot demonstrations.
SE-T-06	iQonic should be able to exchange data with existing infrastructure/assets (legacy systems) at the shop-floor
SE-T-07	A common semantic data modelling.
SE-T-08	Access to physical data using sensors
SE-T-09	The traceability of data collected, and machine/industrial assets observations should be guaranteed.
SE-T-10	iQonic needs to operate in a network-based environment
SE-T-11	The system should leverage standard as much as possible
SE-T-12	The system should not use communication technologies that interfere with existing communication infrastructure
SE-T-13	iQonic platform and communications should be secure
SE-T-14	iQonic system should employ modularity principle.
SE-NT-17	iQonic platform
SE-NT-18	iQonic Data modelling
SA-C-05	The operator or control system shall wait for stationary signal from the electronic nose.
CO-T-01	The machine learning algorithms must have access to synchronized data (common timestamp).

A brief analysis on the requirements (Table 3) shows that the system addresses 11 technical, 3 non-technical, 1 business and 1 constraint requirements in overall. The constraint requirement depicted by the SACMI electronic nose due its operation affecting the transmission frequency of the generated data. The business requirement is addressed by the set of the data defined by each use case (D2.4) for monitoring their process. The union of the technical and non-technical requirements referring to the overall process of the data acquisition and pre-processing performed by the automatic data collection system presented in this report. A special notice should be taken regarding the security of the data transmission and authorization access of the consumers. As depicted in Figure 2, there is a single point of interaction between the ShopFloor, where the field devices exist and thus the data sources and the high-level function (consumers) of the iQonic, the iLike machines platforms. The iLike machine platform (§ 3.5) offers a secure data channel using cryptographic protocols designed to provide communications security over a computer network, while the authorization is performed through channels regulation.

For a detailed report on the requirements see Annex 9.1.

Technical Objective No. 2 - Development of continuous monitoring of the condition and performance.

This continuous monitoring of the multi-stage optoelectronics manufacturing systems will be developed on component and machine level that will enable sustainable and competitive manufacturing, i.e., data management, sensors, processes design and setup as well as defect life-cycle management, disassembly and remanufacturing. Regarding the monitoring at machine level and the collection and aggregation of data from

existing and new sensors, the Internet of Things (IoT) i-Like Machine system of HOLONIX will be employed. Consequently, the online monitoring will be transformed from component to system characterisation during the assembly process chain. The processes itself, the handling-feeding tool, will take care of not only the contamination and defects (i.e., geometrical, semiconductor, layer defects), but also of the optical properties of the (partially) aligned system during assembly operating in real-time covering at least 90% of the production. iQonic will exploit the already installed actuators and sensors, along with the installation of the new sensing equipment provided during the projects life to acquire readings about the machine status, the in-process measurements (e.g. electronic nose, adaptive optics) and the optical sensors to evaluate the quality (high frequency laser).

3.2 iQonic Field Devices

The iQonic Field devices are the devices and sensors located in the ShopFloor or in remote locations used for each Use Case within the iQonic system. In this report, the communication interface of those devices to the ILM – field to cloud communication was examined and implemented through the automatic data collection system. The ITK Daedalus device registration mechanism is responsible for registering the devices to the Local Device Registry (§3.3.2) and the Management Interface (§ 3.4) creates the data flow between the data source and the data consumer (ILM). The registration of the device type and scheme to the ILM is prior to local registration utilizing the API registration of the ILM. The following sections present the field devices (D2.3-§2.3.1) of iQonic system from a communication interface perspective.

3.2.1 ITK Daedalus

The Integra Traceability Kit (ITK) Daedalus Edge device (Figure 7) is a part of the Sensap Swiss AG Integra product line. Through its modular design, Daedalus has a variety of modules that are related to machinery production, besides its core functionality of data acquisition and signal processing unit, as in-Line vision inspection modules for product quality and defect detection and a “smart” Tag module for traceability and automate machine recipe loading (T3.5).

Daedalus integrates with the most popular Enterprise Information Systems (EIS) providing automatic and reliable synchronization of warehouse and shop-floor resources (i.e. labour, equipment, tools, and materials) with standing managerial data, while enabling real-time, remote visibility of operations performance through WEB-based customizable dashboards.

The main functionality of Daedalus within the iQonic system is to act as the IoT gateway and data acquisition system. It will provide the communication connection from the Use Cases Shop floors to the higher-level components (functions) of the iQonic system. Besides that, the ITK will employ a variety of its own sensors (i.e. optical, accelerometers, temperature) in any Demo case needed as defined by the Use case analysis (*D2.4 Use Case Design*).

Based on the Use Cases and each individual demo case, several modules of the ITK Daedalus will be used and new functionalities will be developed within the frame and needs of the iQonic system.

Figure 7 Daedalus Component Diagram

The Daedalus system architecture (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) consists of three components, the Upper-Level Communication Interface, the Low-Level Communication Interface and the Transformation SRV.

The Low-Level communication interface is responsible for interfacing field devices and sensors (data sources) through standards and custom protocols.

The upper-Level communication interface is responsible for the interfacing of the iQonic field devices to the outer world, in this case to the i-Like platform in the cloud.

The Transformation SRV (§ 3.3.1) is responsible for the field device registration, data scheme translation and streaming of the data to the suitable recipient (endpoints).

The positioning of Daedalus in the multi-sensorial network follows the gateway-mediated edge connectivity and management architecture pattern [15] as shown in the **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** Daedalus acts as the endpoint of the wide area network (iQonic high level functions) while isolating the local network of the field devices (edge nodes). This allows for localizing operations and controls. This architecture pattern allows for scaling up in managed assets and in networking. In addition, Daedalus acts as a management point for devices and assets and data aggregation point where some data processing and analytics, and control logic are locally deployed.

Daedalus edge gateway supports the following capabilities:

- *Local connectivity* through wired serial buses and ethernet TCP/IP communications. New communication technologies and protocols are emerging in new deployments.
- *Network and protocol bridging* supporting various data transfer modes between the edge nodes and the wide area network: asynchronous, streaming, and event based.
- *Local data processing* including aggregation, transformation and filtering.
- *Device and asset control and management point* that manages the edge nodes locally.
- *Application logic* that are perform within the local scope.

Figure 8 Gateway-Mediated Edge Connectivity and Management Pattern ([15])

Figure 9: ITK Daedalus architecture

Table 4 summarizes the new functionalities developed within iQonic project during this Task and additional updates/upgrades of the infrastructure of the ITK Daedalus that are needed to support the field devices communication and process monitoring (i.e., Use Case of Filar).

Table 4 ITK Daedalus new Functionalities

Objectives	New and Updated Functionalities
Automated Data acquisition	Transformation Service - <i>New</i>
Data models	Translators - <i>New</i>
Sensors	Different type of sensor (section 4) - <i>Updates</i>
Acquisition network protocol	MQTT-Update, ROS bridge - <i>New</i>

3.2.2 Sacmi Electronic “nose”

The Sacmi Electronic “nose” (D2.3-§2.3.5) provides an external XML webservice, where the instrument sends data without the need for direct access to the electronic nose. The generated data are collected using a SOAP Web client implemented in Daedalus gateway (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Sacmi Electronic Nose -Field to Cloud connection

The device type “SACMI”, as seen in Figure 18, along with its device data series schema (see Annex II: SACMI Data Scheme v1.0) were registered to ILM and the data communication is validated.

3.2.3 FORTH

The adaptive in-line laser raster-scanning optical system provides its data output (D2.3-§2.3.2.3) through an established FTP server within the FORTH facility. An FTP client is implemented and successfully establishes communication with the FORTH system. A schematic is seen in Figure 11, the data series scheme (see FORTH Data Scheme v1.0) includes images. A special consideration needs to be addressed for transferring images in terms of performance and transmission channel bandwidth. An initial approach regarding image encoding and image maximum size is achieved and is currently under development. As this is the case (imaging transfer) in T3.4- Inspection & metrology infrastructure to monitor the KPIs, a joint effort is initiated and work in parallel is under progress.

Figure 11 FORTH - Field to Cloud connection

3.2.4 Shadow Robot

The UR10 + Hand system can be controlled to perform manipulation and grasping actions. The system uses the Robot Operating System (ROS [15]) which uses an anonymous publish/subscribe mechanism to exchange data within ROS system. The Rosbridge provides a JSON API to ROS functionality for non-ROS programs. A Rosbridge client connects through the ROS bridge's WebSocket address and subscribes to the required topics, providing the data outputs (D2.3§2.3.4.3) defined. A first version of the data scheme can be seen in Annex 9.5, the connection to the UR10 + Hand system is under development, employing a virtual machine

using Ubuntu operating system running the active development of ROS Melodic release for the dexterous hand (Figure 12).

Figure 12 Shadow Robots - Field to Cloud connection

3.2.5 ficonTEC

Within the iQonic project two commercially available bonding and assembly machines will be used for the two specific use cases of Prima Electro, as well as for Alpes Laser. The machine for the active lens and mirror alignment for PrimaElectro is based on a standard machine, which is slightly modified within the project in order to fulfil the higher requirements for data logging. The machine for Alpes Laser is based on a conventional bonding machine, however, with substantial development with respect to the new heating oven in the machine. The generated data will be streamed through channels specially developed within the framework of iQonic using well-defined communication protocols (Figure 13). ficonTEC kindly ship to us (Sensap) its main computing unit hosting the application process programming environment upgraded with the communication channels. A proof of concept application was developed with the support of ficonTEC and the assembly process information (required data) by Prima. The evaluated process simulates the first stage of a multi-emitter module assembly, the “Load Module and Check”, where a single diode picked up from its position and electrically tested for emission. The defined data of this process, along with the data generated by the machine (intrinsic data), were successfully acquired through separate channels, processed and published into separate topics at ILM (Annex 9.6 ficonTEC Data Scheme v1.0 -Prima Demo Case(LMC)).

Figure 13 ficonTEC - Field to Cloud connection

3.3 Data Streaming Gateway

A generic approach to the Data Streaming is an efficient mechanism which can receive data from various data sources, process or transform them and finally delivers these data to a set of destination consumers. Within iQonic framework the Data sources are mainly the physical devices, such as a sensor or an asset to the field.

The consumers are mainly the high-level functions within iQonic requesting or consuming the data through iLike platform, which is the main and only consumer of the automatic data collection system.

In conclusion, the Data Streaming subsystem is the background infrastructure which a) enables data processing and b) acts as a proxy for the iLike machine platform.

The adoption of a message bus in the iQonic architecture drives us to the usage of a set of messaging integration patterns for the implementation of Data Streaming subsystem. The Data Streaming subsystem is responsible for receiving data from various source points and delivering them to a set of destination points. In summary, Data Streaming subsystem is the key element for the integration of the field devices to the iLike Machine platform and the rest of the iQonic components, by extending the Message Bus functionality by providing an abstraction level.

Following the publish-subscribe message pattern², it allows for a single data source, that is either a physical or logical device, to stream its data and multiple consumers to process these data. Providing one protocol for data exchange between various field devices or sensors and the iQonic implementation, decouples the development of analytics processes from multi-protocol integrations and allows for the effort to be consumed on the actual analytics processes.

Finally, each logical or physical device, before publishing its data, transforms them - from a “raw data” format, originated from the physical device, - to a new defined format which is based on the data model format described into § 3.5 of this deliverable.

These two functionalities: a) pre-processing data and b) streaming to iLike machines through MQTT, are implemented by the **Routing Transformation Service**. The Data Routing Service simplifies the integration of field devices with the i-Like middleware as it automates functionality, like registration, pre-processing and sending messages.

3.3.1 Routing Transformation Service

The Routing Service enables the interaction with the field devices. The shop floor of the factories that fully address the industry 4.0 [16] paradigm will allow a dynamic configuration of the production line itself. This means that field devices will be enabled/disabled and moved to a different position in the line or in another production line. This dynamic behaviour of the production lines has needs to be addressed regarding the data collection from the physical or logical devices employed. The automatic data collection system will employ and further develop a part of the Data Routing and Pre-processing subsystem that was proposed in FAR-EDGE (D3.2) [17] and enhanced in the PROPHECY CPS Middleware Infrastructure v1 (D3.7) [2].

The Routing Transformation Service provides the following functionality:

- Configure and instantiate a data routing flow and potentially utilize analytics algorithms.

The Routing Transformation Service adopts a number of messaging integration patterns and extends the functionality supported by a message bus. It consists of a) a set of source endpoints b) a set of destination endpoints and c) a management interface. The message bus acts as the Data Routing communication protocol and it is implemented by MQTT which supports publish-subscribe topics.

Source endpoint

Data sources are registered in the local device registry and represented as topics to the message bus. As mentioned above, data sources are the logical representation of any asset on the CPS that produces data (sensor, machine, etc). Data source manifest (DSM) is the instantiation of a data source. As source endpoints are defined, the clients are capable of connecting the data sources with the data flows and are described by the data interface (DI). For every new DI a new client needs to be defined. To the first version of middleware infrastructure, a generic “MQTT channel adapter” is defined as a source endpoint.

Destination endpoint

The destination of the messages provided by the data flow can be either a topic on the message bus or the Streaming Gateway which acts as an endpoint for the iLike Machines. To this version of automatic data collection, the latter type of destination endpoint is defined, a generic MQTT consumer as destination endpoint for the Streaming Gateway component.

² <http://www.enterpriseintegrationpatterns.com/patterns/messaging/PublishSubscribeChannel.html>

The basic concept of messaging is that we have two systems that want to exchange data. The system that sends data is called producer (or sender) and the system that receives data is called consumer (or receiver). Both are called message endpoints. These data are packaged as messages and the producer sends them through a message channel (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Basic concept of messaging [18]

Message

Message is any data record that is packaged to an entity in order to be transmitted through a message channel. For example, based on SACMI (Electronic “Nose”), an iQonic field device, the message is a record of measurements produced by the device.

Message channel

A Message channel is a virtual pipe that connects a sender to a receiver. The system/application sending the data may not know which application will receive the data, but by selecting a particular channel (topic) to send the data, the sender knows that the receiver will be one that is looking for that sort of data by looking for it on that channel. In this way, the applications that produce shared data have a way to communicate with those that wish to consume it.

Message Endpoints

Messaging Endpoint is a client of the messaging system which enables applications to send or receive messages. Usually, applications know nothing about messaging systems. Messaging endpoints receive data from the sender application, transform them to message format and send them to the message channel. Additionally, another endpoint receives messages from message channel, extracts the messages and delivers the data to the receiver application. In general, there are two main types of endpoints: sender and receiver.

3.3.2 Local Device Registry

A physical device is a connected computing device whereas a logical device is a computing process hosted on the physical device. In order to support a multi-protocol environment in the field and provide flexibility and device discoverability in Data Routing, we have designed and implemented a Local Device Registry.

The Local Device Registry supports the multi-protocol and multi-data model field environment by registering the devices including not only their connection endpoints, but also the data models and protocols they support. This way a client or a consumer of a data source, e.g. an analytics process, can discover these protocols and data models and use specific clients and data transformations. Therefore, through the Local Device Registry it is possible for iQonic Edge Gateway processes to connect and acquire data from data sources (devices) following different protocols and data models.

The Local Device Registry decouples underline connection protocols used by the field tier devices and their data representations, thus allowing Edge Gateway to acquire data using various protocol.

The **Local Device Registry** is one of the core components of the Routing Service as it allows for:

- Registering/Unregistering Field Devices
- Exposing Data Formats and Communication Protocols that each Device can support

The Device Registry data model consists of the following entities, adapted and modified for iQonic needs:

- **Data Source (DS):** a logical device that is a data stream *producer*, typically a field sensor or smart machine.

- **Data Consumer (DC):** a logical device that is a data stream *consumer*, typically a data processing algorithm. Within iQonic we have a single consumer, the i-Like Machine platform.
- **Data Kind (DK):** This entity specifies the semantics of the data of the data source, which provides flexibility in modelling different types of data. It can be used to virtually define any type of data in an open and extensible way.
- **Data Interface (DI):** The DI entity is associated with a data source and provides the information needed to connect to it and access its data, including details like network protocol, port, network address and more.
- **Data Source Definition (DSD):** This entity defines the properties of a data source of the system, such as a data stream from a sensor, an automation device or even an analytics algorithm. It sets a subject, by referencing a well-known DK³ and a protocol, to connect to data sources of that type. The protocol specifications are defined inside a **Data Interface Specification (DI)** structure, which contains a) the protocol details and b) the declaration of available connection parameters, if required.
- **Processor Definition (PD):** This entity specifies a processing function to be applied on one or more data sources. It can be used to set up a data routing flow and to utilize analytics algorithms as well.
- **Data Source Manifest (DSM):** The DSM entity specifies a specific instance of a data source in-line with its DSD and DI specifications. Multiple manifests (i.e. DSMs) are therefore used to represent the data sources that are available in the factory in the scope of the iQonic data generation. It also declares the MAC address of the device.
- **Data Channel Descriptor (DCD):** Data Channel Descriptor (DCD) represents an established network communication channel, uniquely identified by a UUID between a data source and a data consumer.
- **Live Data Set (LDS):** The LDS represents the actual data/measurement that stem from an instance of a data source that is represented through a DSM. Hence, it references a DSM that drives the specification of the types of the attributes of the LiveDataSet. A LiveDataSet is associated with a timestamp and keeps track of the location of the data source in case it is associated with a mobile (rather than a stationary) data source. Hence, it has a location attribute as well.

Exposing its functionality as a REST Web Service, it defines the model entities as Resources (represented as URLs) and allows CRUD actions through the HTTP's GET, POST, PUT and DELETE. The service invocation's request and response payloads are represented as JSON documents. The resources that have been identified are:

- /registry-repo/ProcessorManifest
- /registry-repo/DataSourceDefinition
- /registry-repo/DataSourceManifest
- /registry-repo/DataKind

All these resources are kept in the Registry Repo Database.

3.3.3 Translators

The Translators are a stack of functions/classes mapping the data schemes defined by the data sources (field devices) to a canonical data model defined by the iLike Machine platform. It enables the various field devices by different vendors to exchange data with the other components of the iQonic system. Potentially, as an add on value it could permit the exchange of data among field devices as well, with minor effort.

i-Like Machines Data model

The data scheme defined by the iLike machine is of JSON type aligned with the Apache AVRO scheme. This scheme is a data serialization system that provides,

- Rich data structures.

³ DK entries do not need to be physically stored anywhere: they are assumed to be a shared notion within any given system, and their identifying URI to be a local convention.

- A compact, fast, binary data format.
- A container file, to store persistent data.
- Remote procedure call (RPC).
- Simple integration with dynamic languages.

In addition, When Avro data are read, the schema used when writing it is always present. This permits each datum to be written with no per-value overheads, making serialization both fast and small. This also facilitates use with dynamic scripting languages, since data - together with their schema - are fully self-describing. An example of a validated Apache AVRO data scheme can be found in Annex 9.2

Raw Data

Raw data (source data) are data that has not been processed for use. A distinction is sometimes made between data and information to the effect that information is the end product of data processing. Raw data that has undergone processing are sometimes referred to as cooked data. Although raw data has the potential to become "information," they require selective extraction, organization, and sometimes analysis and formatting for presentation. In this task and within iQonic framework, the raw data were processed, aggregated and translated to the canonical data model. As an example, the raw data generated by a single axis accelerometer are a hexadecimal number (digital output). This number needs to be processed, formatted and translated to a significant value with a physical meaning to be further analysed and used by the other systems of the iQonic platform. A more detailed example can be found in Annex 9.7.

Figure 15 ITK Daedalus internal structure

3.4 Management Interface

Finally, the management interface is the core component of the Routing Transformation Service and is responsible for configuring and executing the data flows from one source endpoint to another destination endpoint. The functionality of the Management Interface is exposed through the following REST interface:

- HTTP POST /routing/processor: Creates and executes a data flow based on a processor manifest (PM). The source endpoint of the data flow is chosen by the data Source DSM, while the destination endpoint is defined by sink DSM. The sequence diagram of all actions is depicted in Figure 16.
- HTTP DELETE /routing/ processor/processorId: Stops the data flow for the PM with id= processorId.

Figure 16 Create a new data flow: sequence diagram

3.5 Interfacing with Holonix platform

The i-Like Machines (ILM) is an industrial IoT platform for fleet management, diagnostic and analytics of industrial assets and enabling monitoring. It offers a suite of components for retrieving, organising and visualising, almost in real time, all the data that are relevant to know the history and the current status of a machine/system. An example of the current functionalities of I-LiKe Machines is provided in Figure 17. These components can be combined to offer customised solutions to the machine users, enabling them to monitor the status of the production machine and alerting them in case of problems. I-LiKe Machines offers also interesting opportunities to the machine producers, supporting them in improving after sales services but also providing them valuable information on the behaviour of their products. The core of the solution consists of a set of gateways to read data from the field, a cloud platform to store and elaborate data, and a set of web and mobile apps to present the data to the users.

Figure 17 Machine monitoring using I-LiKe Machines

The cloud platform is in charge of the following four main tasks:

- Storing of the relevant information collected during the machine lifecycle.
- Maintaining a complete representation, at any moment, of the machine status.
- Keeping track of the machine status history.
- Detecting machines alarms and anomalous conditions and notify the users and maintainers about them.

The relevant machines parameters are selected together with the machines users/producers. Examples include Timestamp, Power on time, Working time, Cycle time, Operating speed of the stations, etc. In order to feed the cloud platform, data must be collected from the machines and production lines. This is achieved by implementing a software component (gateway) that talks to the machine, does the basic computations that are easy to be performed with low latency access to the machine and sends the data in a secure way to the cloud platform adhering to its API. This part is often customised to the specific machine, as protocols might change across various machines types and might be proprietary. It can reside on hardware already present on the machines or on embedded systems added on purpose.

Considering iQonic project and related aims, the ILM supports multiple configuration topologies for the field devices and data streaming. In this deliverable, the following approach was adapted (Figure 18), employing the twofold operation of ITK Daedalus both as a gateway and as a device. The main specifications and guidelines of ILM for the “Field to Cloud” layers of the IoT stack, allowing data collected from the “field” to be carried to the cloud infrastructure where they can be stored and processed, are reported.

Key concepts:

Multi-tenancy

For resources optimization, i-LiKe Machines can operate in multitenant mode. In respect of the field to cloud communication a tenant defines an isolated environment dedicated to a customer or a project. I-LiKe Machines does not provide a built-in method to transfer data from one tenant to another.

Device Types

They are a logical grouping of devices that share common traits, typically mapping to types of equipment. Devices are hereby instances of a given *device type*.

Data series and schemas

A device type contains also the definitions of the message types that will be exchanged in form of data series. They have a unique name within the device type, a schema that describes the structure of the exchanged data and a set of parameters that control how the data will be treated.

Typically, data series map to the collection of parameters that share functional meaning, data types and sampling time.

Enforcement of a schema is a focal point of communication. It ensures that no unexpected data is processed within the platform and establishes a contract between the parties implementing the field and the cloud sides of the communication.

Figure 18 ILM Delegated Mode: Daedalus acts as the main gateway to be used by multiple devices.

As seen in Figure 18, Daedalus is mapped as a gateway and provides access to different types of field devices. It has a well-defined source of data, so it is mapped as a device type as well. The registration of the Device Types and thus the instantiation of a Device take place through the registry API of the ILM.

MQTT Connection

The transmission of the data happens through an MQTT broker with TLS certificate and user credentials access.

Message structure

The message is in JSON format and is composed by two different parts:

```
{
  "t": <UNIX_TIME_MILLISECONDS>,
  "d": <PAYLOAD>
}
```

The first part is the envelope of the message, that defines the two properties “t”, the timestamp of the message as Unix timestamp in milliseconds and “d”, the actual message payload.

The value of the “d” property must comply to the Avro schema associated with the data series. For instance, consider SACMI data series in Annex 9.2 named “general” and a valid payload in Annex 9.8

Multiple topics

Finally, the ILM supports multiple topics to be created related to each demo case and process. For instance, in Use Case of Prima, where a ficonTEC machine will perform multiple processes on the assembly line phase, the generated data will be published in topics per processes (i.e. FAC topic). In addition to that, topics related to data kind (i.e., motion, environment) will be available.

4 Sensors

In this Task, apart from the automatic data collection of the data specified in WP2 and WP3, an analysis of each demo case in use cases was conducted to define additional needed sensors for monitoring the processes and supporting the requirements of the high-level functions of the iQonic. A major contribution to this work was through D2.4 Use Case Design which acts as a reference document for all the technical developments carried out within WP3-WP6 in the iQonic project.

In this section, the additional defined sensors for the demo cases are presented in overall.

4.1 Vibration

The need of vibration measurements in critical and strategic locations were defined and ITK Daedalus was upgraded with the following vibration sensors:

- Hansford (0-100)g and (0-5)g
- XDK Bosch

The vibration sensor from Hansford Sensors is a single axis accelerometer with a 0-100 g sensitivity. Its main purpose is to detect and log peak values of acceleration throughout the monitoring process. Additional vibration sensors of the same type were acquired with 0-5g sensitivity for logging vibrations during the process. In addition, it has an embedded a temperature sensor and its enclosure is isolated and industrial rated.

The XDK Bosch offers:

- Accelerometer: BMA280
- Gyroscope: BMG160
- Magnetometer: BMM150
- Environmental sensors
 - Combined humidity / temperature / air pressure sensor: BME280
 - Ambient light: MAX44009
 - Microphone for noise detection: AKU340

Finally, data communication takes place through Low power IEEE 802.11b/g/n WLAN and Bluetooth Low Energy, offering a mobility and an “easy” to relocate capability. This will be very usefully in the integration phase (WP7) if a need for additional vibration sensors - or relocation of the installed - emerged through a first analysis of the collected data.

4.2 Environmental

An Amphenol humidity and temperature sensor designed for reliability in harsh environment with a ± 2 % RH and ± 0.5 °C and low current consumption was chosen. The sensor is calibrated and tested ready to be used without further calibration or temperature compensation. The environmental sensing is enriched with the XDK Bosh embedded environmental sensors, where the first one (Amphenol) provide us with environmental data of the place that the monitored process was executed (ambient), while the second one provides us with environmental data from local positions, even on the machine itself.

4.3 Various Types

In addition, ITK Daedalus was updated with modules and sensors for

- Measuring electrical characteristic (i.e., current, voltage) of a load
- Magnetic sensor for linear displacement measurement with a repeat accuracy of max. ± 1 μ m
- Load cell, transforming pressure (force) into an electrical signal.

5 Demo Cases

Through the technical visits to the Demonstrators (ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR) within the phase 1 “Building a common knowledge on the initial state of the iQonic Use-Cases” of T2.4 and the dedicated teleconferences for each Use Cases, we successfully position the iQonic architecture and implement a prototype version of the automatic data collection system.

5.1 Filar Optomaterials

FILAR is a reliable supplier of photonic and optical materials manufacturing, representing big industrial sectors of supplying optical (synthetic) and laser crystals. By introducing the iQonic, FILAR expects to benefit by adding value to both on-line and off-line monitoring of the process chains by seeking more accurate feedback for deeper understanding and analysis.

A summary of the preliminary ideas related to this task emerged during the technical visit in Filar shown in (Table 1Table 5), the process that iQonic will address is the Ultrasound Machining (USM). The process is basically a discrete control (manually driven) while a real time process control could be implemented. Nevertheless, in this use case we defined the needed sensors for monitoring the USM process. The digitization phase of the use case was a joint work with related WP’s (WP5, WP6) and with the support and guidance of FILAR.

Table 5 Preliminary set of solutions identified during the Filar brainstorming session.

WP	Preliminary ideas
4	<p>Sensors for enabling model-based process control</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors for ultrasonic machining (USM) process: Microphone (acoustic emissions), weight of the part, speed of cut. • Data collection from USM: amplitude, frequency. • Need for a knowledge-based system for collecting process data in comprehensive way. • Possibility to use XRD for cutting oriented crystals. • Centering before drilling. • On-line identification of the crystal axis.

The additional defined sensors (Table 6) along with the additional modules and related firmware upgrade of ITK Daedalus (INTEGRA ITK-SR4U-H) will be installed in Filar facility, completing this way the digitization phase of the USM process.

Table 6 Defined Sensors for Filar Use Case

Sensor	Function
microphone/acoustic	Emergency Stop, 65 db threshold
accelerometers	Observation of the vibrations on real time basis, Position
Linear distance	Tip position, feed rate
Optical/Vision System	Measurement of the real tip length during the process
accelerometers	Vibration Analysis
accelerometers/Temp	Vibration Analysis
weight	Regulate Constant Pressure
Temp/Humidity Ambient	Process Conditions
Digital 'Clock'	Replace Analog Sensor/Digitized reading

Electrical Data-Current -Voltage

5.2 Prima Electro

PRIMA Electro is a division of PRIMA INDUSTRIE Group that is a worldwide leader in the field of the laser machinery for the metal sheet cutting and welding applications in 2D and 3D. PE is ELECTRONIC AND LASER DIVISION, dedicated industrial-level solutions, high-tech electronics, numerical controls and motion systems, high-power laser sources for industrial applications. In the last years PE has been dedicated to the production of laser diodes, with a plant completely dedicated to this purpose. Through iQonic, Prima Electro is planning to achieve optimised configurations of the diodes that will make it possible to overcome customisation limits, exploiting in an efficient way the laser process for different applications, according to the features of the beam.

Besides the technical visit to Prima, a series of teleconference was conducted between Prima and involved partners. The support of Prima with their in-depth knowledge of the process along with the technical support of ficonTEC and the work from the related deliverables (D2.2, D2.3, D2.4 and D2.5) lead to a first prototype of the data collection, utilizing a ficonTEC machine by Prima for the multi-emitter series (Figure 19) and the collected data were successfully transmitted to the ILM platform.

Figure 19 Prima Demo Case – utilizing ficonTEC machine

6 Conclusions and Next Actions

The automatic data collection system following the overall iQonic concept [1] through the iQonic architecture [9], supporting the user requirements and each use case demands (D2.4, D2.5), proved to be a demanding task with multidiscipline extensions. As it was stated thoroughly in the D2.4 Use case design the cultural gap among the two communities, the experts on opto-electronics components and the Zero-Defect Manufacturing experts was a barrier that through the several visits to Demonstrators (ALPES, PRIMA, FILAR) and to laser experts (HiLase) led us to gain in depth knowledge of the opto-electronics assembly processes and hands on experience.

In this deliverable, based on the DoA objectives, the iQonic sensorial network was defined via an overview of the iQonic multi-sensorial network architecture and infrastructure that provided the architecture of the infrastructure that is responsible for the automatic data collection including the supported requirements specifications and the field devices employed in the iQonic system. Furthermore, the Data Streaming sub-system that is responsible for managing the data streaming operations and registering the data sources was analysed in detail. The use cases for the automatic data collection infrastructure were presented along with the discussion concerning the additional sensors that were defined for the use cases. Regarding the related milestones of this deliverable, the iQonic platform communication integration has been achieved for the electronic Noise (SACMI), while for Adaptive Optics (FORTH) it is still in progress along with the virtual integration regarding communication for the Handling Tool (Shadow Robots), concluding the MS5 (M4.1)-M19: In-line sensors and Handling tool are ready (SENSAP) related milestone. Finally, concerning the MS6 (M4.2)-M19: KBS and Data management system (HOLONIX) milestone, the connection regarding the infrastructure and the data from the sensors and actuators relating to the KBS has been achieved.

In conclusion, the next steps and actions following this deliverable include addressing further user requirements, validating the transmission of images (encoding, method) due to large size and finally as mentioned above, implementing the iQonic platform communication integration for Shadow Robots and FORTH.

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex I: Supported Requirements

RQ ID	PR-B-03	RQ Type	Business	Use Cases	PRIMA			
Parent Requirement	N/A							
Title (Summary)	Process Monitoring: Disassembly, Remanufacturing & Reuse of the components, currently, these aspects are not managed due to the higher vertical production and the high operating costs.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Through iQonic it will be possible to have an optimization of these three phases, thanks to real-time monitoring and better data management along the process steps. Monitoring is a strategic point for process management and complete traceability from the initial phase to the final phase of the diode production process. Monitor means collecting data for zero defect manufacturing. This will save on the waste of the raw material, also influencing the final cost of the components.							
Reporter	PRIMA		Assignee	iQonic Consortium				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	26.11.2018.							

RQ ID	AT-T-11	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	Data shall be collected and analysed for monitoring of iQonic strategies implementation.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Both iQonic component level development (vertical) and process chains implementation level (horizontal) will be implemented at each pilot use case scenario and system operational environment. Furthermore, process chain status measurement analysis will be adapted to provide the means for process validation.							
Reporter	ATLANTIS		Assignee	FRAUNHOFER, ATLANTIS				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	30.11.2018.							

RQ ID	AT-NT-13	RQ Type	Non-Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
--------------	----------	----------------	---------------	------------------	-----------------------------------

Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	Data shall be collected and organized from pilot demonstrations.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The data for technical, user acceptance and factory impact indicators shall be gathered in different formats (rtf documents for user acceptance, questionnaires / online instruments, spreadsheets with data for technical KPIs, data of ERP-MES-SCADA repositories, data from impact checklists), organized from pilot demonstrations.							
Reporter	ATLANTIS			Assignee		FRAUNHOFER, ATLANTIS		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (history)	30.11.2018.							

RQ ID	SE-T-06	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic should be able to exchange data with existing infrastructure/assets (legacy systems) at the shop-floor							
Rationale (why, what, how)	A layer that facilitate the data exchange, flow and sharing between software components/services, based on industrial standards (e.g. OPC UA) should be designed and developed.							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss			Assignee		SENSAP		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-07	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	SE-T-06							
Title (Summary)	A common semantic data modelling.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Modelling of the data to be exchanged by the acquisition module to the upper level sub-systems of the iQonic should be designed and agreed between involved partners.							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss			Assignee		SENSAP, HOLONIX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-08	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	Access to physical data using sensors							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The iQonic will provide the necessary mechanisms for sensing (i.e. to extract information from heterogenous data sources both physical and software assets)							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss		Assignee	SENSAP				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-09	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	The traceability of data collected, and machine/industrial assets observations should be guaranteed.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	All the data collected and extracted from machines/industrial assets must be related to a standard reference system to enable the connection, mapping and tracking of the extracted data and observations to machines/industrial assets, data analytics services, etc.							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss		Assignee	SENSAP, HOLONIX, ATLANTIS				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-10	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic needs to operate in a network-based environment							
Rationale (why, what, how)	To use web-based technologies to allow all the components and layers within the system to connect with other part of the system itself that is available in the same network							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss		Assignee	FRAUNHOFER				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No

Date (change history)	02/01/2019
------------------------------	------------

RQ ID	SE-T-11	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	The system should leverage standard as much as possible							
Rationale (why, what, how)	To design and develop a layer that deeply relies on standards to support and facilitate the integration of legacy and heterogeneous machines/industrial assets							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss		Assignee	FRAUNHOFER, SENSAP, TUT				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-12	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE			
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	To design, develop and install a "non" intrusive system							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The system should not use communication technologies that interfere with existing communication infrastructure							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss		Assignee	FRAUNHOFER, SENSAP, TUT				
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-13	RQ Type	Technical	Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE
Parent RQ	N/A				
Title (Summary)	iQonic platform and communications should be secure				
Rationale (why, what, how)	Several data sources generate data that needs to be collected and sent over public and/or private networks to a possibly remote infrastructure in order to be analysed. In the same way, data generated on a remote location received back to the iQonic module in order to integrate the received information into the process				
Reporter	Sensap Swiss		Assignee	FRAUNHOFER, SENSAP, HOLONIX	

Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	02/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-T-14	RQ Type	Technical		Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic system should employ modularity principle.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	System components should be loosely coupled and reconfigurable on a plug and play principle so as the system be able to respond to changing customer requirements and overcome internal system failures.							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss			Assignee	FRAUNHOFER			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No
Date (change history)	09/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-NT-17	RQ Type	Non-technical		Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic platform							
Rationale (why, what, how)	Architecture shall comply with the emerging standards (RAMI 4.0 and the Industrial Internet Consortium)							
Reporter	Sensap Swiss			Assignee	FRAUNHOFER			
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	11/01/2019							

RQ ID	SE-NT-18	RQ Type	Non-technical		Use Cases	ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	iQonic Data modelling							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The semantics of modelling in iQonic must be based on standardized meta-models and ontologies and should support the production and be extensible.							

Reporter	Sensap Swiss			Assignee		FRAUNHOFER. ATLANTIS, HOLONIX		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	Yes	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	11/01/2019							

RQ ID	CO-T-01	RQ Type		Technical	Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	The machine learning algorithms must have access to synchronized data (common timestamp).							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The common timestamp will ensure that the data from the sensors and machines can be properly matched with each other to identify anomalies.							
Reporter	CORE			Assignee		HOLONIX, ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	Yes	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	No	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	21/12/2018							

RQ ID	SA-C-05	RQ Type		Constraint	Use Cases		ALPES, FILAR, PRIMA, BRIGHTERWAVE	
Parent RQ	N/A							
Title (Summary)	The operator or control system shall wait for stationary signal from the electronic nose.							
Rationale (why, what, how)	The scope of this constraint is to inform the users on timing for the sampling, If the sampling time is not long enough to achieve a stationary signal, the output could not be representative of the sample. Approximately 5-10 minutes are required before starting sampling since the gas sample is presented to the electronic nose, or a change in measurement conditions occurs. As a consequence, the sampling rate of the device is not higher than one sample (or one batch of samples) every 5 minutes. Incorrect measurements can be generated if the operator does not wait the requested time because he/she is not informed, or the process of the user does not allow to wait 5 to 10 minutes.							
Reporter	SACMI			Assignee		ALL		
Priority	<i>Essential</i>	No	<i>Major</i>	No	<i>Medium</i>	Yes	<i>Optional</i>	No
Date (change history)	10/12/2018							

9.2 Annex II: SACMI Data Scheme v1.0

```
{
  "type": "record",
  "name": "general",
  "fields": [
    {
      "type": "long",
      "name": "Id"
    },
    {
      "type": "t",
      "name": "dateTime"
    },
    {
      "type": "string",
      "name": "Label1"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "Code1"
    },
    {
      "type": "decimal",
      "name": "Perc1"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "Conc1"
    },
    {
      "type": "string",
      "name": "Label2"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "Code2"
    },
    {
      "type": "decimal",
      "name": "Perc2"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "Conc2"
    },
    {
      "type": "string",
      "name": "Label3"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "Code3"
    },
    {
      "type": "decimal",
      "name": "Perc3"
    },
  ],
}
```



```
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "Conc3"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "TExt"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "DPExt"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "WS"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "WD"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "WTxt"
},
{
  "type": "boolean",
  "name": "Err"
},
{
  "type": "int",
  "name": "SystemId"
},
{
  "type": "int",
  "name": "SourceId"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "Conf1"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "Conf2"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "Conf3"
}
]
}
```


9.3 ITK Daedalus Data Scheme v1.0

```

{
  "type": "record",
  "name": "general",
  "fields": [
    {
      "type": "string",
      "name": "Id"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "submissionTime"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "aquisitionTimeDig"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "prdcbot"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "prdrate"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "prd_speed"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "uptime"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "downtime"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "idletime"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "setuptime"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "errbot"
    },
    {
      "type": "t",
      "name": "aquisitionTimeAn"
    },
    {
      "type": "string",

```



```
        "name": "status"
      },
      {
        "type": "float",
        "name": "tempHS"
      },
      {
        "type": "array",
        "items": "float",
        "name": "vibHS"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

9.4 FORTH Data Scheme v1.0

```
{
  "type": "record",
  "name": "recipe",
  "fields": [
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "wavelength"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "power"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "excitpolar"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "magn"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "sizepx"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "points"
    }
  ]
}
```



```
  },
  {
    "type": "float",
    "name": "voltage"
  },
  {
    "type": "int",
    "name": "bp"
  },
  {
    "type": "float",
    "name": "voltageamp"
  }
]
}
{
  "type": "record",
  "name": "output",
  "fields": [
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "digadptedz"
    },
    {
      "type": "bool",
      "name": "rasterscanimgmicro"
    },
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "direcdetpolar"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "pxbybxorient"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "pxbypbx"
    }
  ]
}
```



```
]
}
```

9.5 Shadow Data Scheme v1.0

```
{
  "type": "record",
  "name": "general",
  "fields": [
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "id"
    },
    {
      "type": "string",
      "name": "process"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "J1"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "J2"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "J3"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "J4"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "J5"
    },
    {
      "type": "float",
      "name": "J6"
    },
  ],
}
```



```
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "T1"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "T2"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "T3"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "T4"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "T5"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "DCP1"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "DCP2"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "DCP3"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "DCP4"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "DCP5"
}
```



```
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "AccX"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "AccY"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "AccZ"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "GyroX"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "GyroY"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "GyroZ"
}
]
}
```

9.6 ficonTEC Data Scheme v1.0 -Prima Demo Case(LMC)

```
{
  "type": "record",
  "name": "general",
  "fields": [
    {
      "type": "int",
      "name": "index"
    },
    { "type": "int",
      "name": "timestamp"
    },
  ],
}
```



```
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "OperName"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "Assembly_Main"
},
{ "type": "int",
  "name": "StatusID"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "LasStatusDesc"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "Serie"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "PN"
},
{
  "type": "int",
  "name": "Laser"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "J_Number"
},
{
  "type": "string",
  "name": "EmitterName"
},
{
  "type": "float",
  "name": "LV"
}
```



```

    ]
}

```

9.7 1-Axis accelerometer Raw Data to Canonical data model Example

9.8 SACMI valid payload

```

"d": {
  "id": 2991574,
  "label1": "AIR",
  "code1": 15,
  "perc1": 85.8,
  "conc1": 100.0,
  "label2": "TRANSITION",
  "code2": 13,
  "perc2": 9.3,
  "conc2": 100,
  "label3": "compsolf",
  "code3": 0,
  "perc3": 4.7,
  "conc3": 54.088253,
  "tExt": 24.0,
  "dpExt": 12.8,
  "ws": 0,
  "wd": 243.7,
  "wTxt": "WSW",
  "err": true,

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"systemId": 50,  
"sourceId": 0,  
"conf1": 0,  
"conf2": 0,  
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}
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